

Project Title	Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative
Project Acronym	digiNEB.eu
Project Number	101083743
Type of project	Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL)
Topics	DIGITAL-2021-DEPLOY-01-BAUHAUS
Starting date of Project	1 October 2022
Duration of the project	24 months
Website	www.digineb.eu

D4.1 - Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report – initial version

Work Package	WP4 Adoption and Synergies
Task	T4.1 Stakeholder Engagement
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Version	V1.0
Due Date	31.12.2022
Submission Date	01/02/2023

Dissemination Level

X	PU: Public
	SEN: Sensitive
	R-UE/EU-R: EU Classified
	C-UE/EU-C: EU Classified
	S-UE/EU-S: EU Classified

digiNEB.eu – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

Versioning History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	05/12/2022	Michela Magas (ICF), Sten-Erik Björling (ICF), Jan Aman (ICF), Florence Kuijl (Innovawood), Uwe Kies (Innovawood), Roberto Cavallo (EAAE), Mar Muñoz Aparici (EAAE), Georg Vrachliotis (TU Delft), Claudio de Majo (Trust-IT), Maria Giuffrida (Trust-IT)	Collection of text inputs from partners
0.2	16/12/2022	Andrew Dubber (ICF)	First draft
0.3	05/01/2023	Michela Magas (ICF), Franklin van der Hoeven (TU Delft), Silvana Muscella (Trust-IT)	Review and additions
0.4	12/01/2023	Andrew Dubber (ICF)	Second draft
0.5	16/01/2023	Michela Magas (ICF)	Review
0.6	17/01/2023	Andrew Dubber (ICF)	Third draft
0.7	17/01/2023	Michela Magas (ICF)	Review
0.8	17/01/2023	Andrew Dubber (ICF)	Review and minor additions
0.9	18/01/2023	Silvana Muscella Rita Giuffrida, Claudio De Majo, Paolo Lombardi (Trust-IT).	Restructuring of the TOC, added Sec. 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9. Added text to all sections.
0.91	26/01/2023	Andrew Dubber (ICF), Michela Magas (ICF)	Review
0.92	25/01/2023	Michela Magas (ICF)	comments addressed
0.93	26/01/2023	Michela Magas (ICF)-	comments addressed
0.94	26/01/2023	Andrew Dubber (ICF), Michela Magas (ICF)	Review
0.95	27/01/2023	Silvana Muscella (Trust-IT)	comments addressed
0.96	28/01/2023	Andrew Dubber (ICF), Michela Magas (ICF)	comments addressed and text consolidated
0.97	29/01/2023	Franklin van der Hoeven (TU DELFT)	Quality Check
0.98	30/01/2023	Maria Giuffrida (Trust-IT), Florence Kuijl (Innovawood)	Peer Review
1.0	31/01/2023	Michela Magas (ICF), Andrew Dubber (ICF)	Version 1.0 completed, addressing comments from quality check & final touch-ups before submission to the EC.

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DMS	Document Management System
DTPC	Deputy Technical Project Coordinator
EAG	External Advisory Group
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FACL	Financial & Administrative Coordinator Leader
GA	Grant Agreement
KOM	Kick-off meeting
LCMS	Learning Content Management System
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PMB	Project Management Board
R&I	Research and Innovation
SG	Stakeholder Group
The Consortium	All the Project Partners, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + COMMpla + EAAE + ICF + IW
The Project Beneficiaries	The signatory Partners of the Grant Agreement, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TL	Task Leader
TPC	Technical Project Coordinator
TWG	Technical Working Group
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Keywords

Community, engagement, platform, multidisciplinary, stakeholder, engagement, risk, responsibility

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

The digiNEB.eu project supports the implementation of the New European Bauhaus (NEB) and the speeding up of the green transformation by increasing the adoption of NEB digital solutions. digiNEB.eu is a Coordination Action, and as such, it is imperative to identify and understand stakeholder needs to respond to them and provide the required knowledge support, networking, upskilling and community participation. This document outlines the engagement objectives, target stakeholder groups, engagement channels, risks, and partners' engagement roles and responsibilities for the digiNEB.eu initiative.

The digiNEB.eu platform aims to increase stakeholder understanding of the New European Bauhaus, keep stakeholders well-informed, contribute to the digital transformation, disseminate NEB best practices, enable cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration, monitor the global impact of NEB and inform standardisation and policy.

The Stakeholder Engagement Plan goes beyond addressing a catalogue of the traditional target groups that might ordinarily be expected when joining digital stakeholders with particular areas of specialism (architects, designers, educators...). Following partner consultations, the plan has been evolved with a new approach that draws together multidisciplinary communities around a series of topics of common interest. This approach builds upon an effective NEB strategy established in NEB projects such as Nordic Carbon-Neutral Bauhaus and Bauhaus Goes South. Each of these has developed a large stakeholder pool around a central theme that different stakeholders relate to. Aligning topics around the missions of these established communities provides an effective method for onboarding large numbers of NEB stakeholders. The aim is to align multiple and diverse digital technology research communities with these established NEB communities; build trust, encourage engagement, particularly between silos; and ensure two-way dialogues and multidisciplinary co-creation rather than simply one-way dissemination.

Following this onboarding strategy, the proposed Technology Working Groups (TWGs) have been reframed around topics and renamed as Thematic Working Groups. This allows digiNEB.eu to build on NEB's mission-driven strategy and gather digital and NEB communities around a series of common themes, allowing for greater inclusivity and contributions beyond the specific categories of stakeholders identified in the project proposal, divided into seven categories (architects, construction industry, researchers, policymakers, etc.). The first event that will test this method of onboarding communities is being hosted by CERN IdeaSquare and will gather 50 NEB and digital stakeholders in-person over 2.5 days in co-creation workshops.

The digiNEB.eu project has already implemented and is in the process of further implementing knowledge exchange and matchmaking events, webinars, educational seminars and hands-on innovation labs, place-based education, social media, and the activation and empowerment of early adopters. Results from engagement and knowledge creation will be transferred to the digital platform, which will provide databases, catalogues and toolkits. It will conduct community-building events, incentivise Early Adopters as ambassadors, publish success stories, offer a useful co-creation space along with valuable digital resources and assets, and amplify impacts through social media channels.

Engagement with stakeholders will be the responsibility of all members of the digiNEB.eu consortium. Linking with partners' existing networks and connections will be a central aspect of this outreach. In addition, each partner will have a specific focal area to share the workload and leverage key strengths, as well as to avoid duplication.

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1. Introduction

The digiNEB.eu project seeks to create an open, inclusive platform that encourages collaboration and communication between stakeholders to support cross-fertilisation between the digital industry and all NEB disciplines. The digiNEB.eu stakeholder engagement aims to enable stakeholders to share knowledge and build trust while also helping to keep track of the evolution of digital and New European Bauhaus innovations and feeding best practices from co-creation between the engaged communities back into policy. Therefore, identifying and understanding stakeholder needs is fundamental to promoting and ensuring community participation.

Community onboarding and analysis of their needs will inform the evolution of the digital **toolkit** that will provide practical digital solutions for the community implementation of the Green Deal. Innovative results from the digiNEB.eu community will populate the digiNEB.eu **Observatory**, including access to a collection of EU-funded initiatives related to the New European Bauhaus, as well as Thematic Working Groups (TWGs). The TWGs bring together high-level experts from within the NEB digital ecosystem, as well as the broader digiNEB.eu multidisciplinary community to exchange knowledge on best practices and formulate strategic policy recommendations. In addition, the platform aims to provide access to best practice guides and training materials, delivered as freely available e-learning courses. Engagement with the tools on the platform will help identify the early adopters who can act as project ambassadors, help identify gaps in the NEB digital ecosystem and seek solutions that may address them. Early Adopters will increase project visibility and maximise further external engagement.

2. Engagement Objectives

Widespread use of the digiNEB.eu platform and toolkit is part of the goal of stakeholder engagement. The ethos of the New European Bauhaus requires that stakeholders become more than an atomised cloud of individual users but rather active community participants. This participation requires building trust within a diverse group of potential users and stakeholders, and engagement must occur transversally. Trust must be built between silos and among stakeholders from diverse knowledge domains and backgrounds – not simply between each user and the platform but amongst the many kinds of users. Key to this level of engagement is a platform that allows for two-way communication, with dialogue and co-creation as central to the action, rather than one-way dissemination. Initiating the dialogue will involve reaching out to NEB partners and engaging with projects, becoming well-informed of existing activities and projects, transforming digital business models using NEB principles, connecting across domains and fostering interdisciplinary understanding, and monitoring the evolution of NEB in the global context.

One of the main goals of digiNEB.eu is to interlink and unite the NEB community by providing specific mechanisms to identify, segment, and reach out to complementary stakeholder groups.

To that end, digiNEB.eu has elaborated a comprehensive Engagement Strategy for the project, focusing on tackling Engagement Objectives, Target Stakeholder Groups, Engagement Channels, Risks and Mitigations, and the digiNEB.eu Partners' Engagement Roles and Responsibilities. In doing so, assumptions about the needs and use cases of stakeholders, as well as about the nature and potential of the project, were questioned, and accordingly, the ambition and focus of the digiNEB.eu project's stakeholder engagement were expanded, as will be demonstrated below.

2.1. Increase understanding between the New European Bauhaus and Smart Communities

The digiNEB.eu initiative seeks to create a platform for two-way communication, with dialogue and co-creation central to the process. Of primary importance is clarifying what the New European Bauhaus is and what it represents to current and potential future stakeholders.

Understanding how NEB creates meaning for stakeholders involves reaching out to all NEB partners and engaging with existing and developing projects active in the New European Bauhaus ecosystem. Connection with NEB Lab projects and **NEB lighthouse projects** (see 6.1) provides the digiNEB.eu Coordination Action with an already extensive network of engaged and active stakeholders. Second, attention to innovative tools devised in both the public and private sectors at the European level is essential to enhance the project's outreach and its platform, provided that these innovations are aligned with NEB's three main principles of sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics.

2.2. Increase capacity for all involved stakeholders

A key objective of the stakeholder engagement strategy is to become and remain constantly well-informed of existing NEB activities and projects on the ground that may have an impact on or are of direct relevance to digital platform creators. In their capacity as Early Adopters, successful NEB community projects are to be actively involved in digiNEB.eu co-creation activities with digital communities for capacity building and contributions to effective Green Deal solutions. The digiNEB.eu programme includes a variety of methods for capacity building, including regular webinars, co-creation events, and contribution to the new NEB Academy (see 2.5).

2.3. Contribute to the digital transformation from multiple perspectives

Since the engagement strategy is not merely one of dissemination but also of providing tools and positive benefits for users engaging with the digiNEB.eu digital toolkit, a key objective is for close collaboration between NEB and digital stakeholders in co-creation activities that will address digitalisation challenges from both the digitalisation and NEB perspectives. This creates an opportunity for Early Adopter NEB communities to contribute to the digital agenda from the sustainability, usability and accessibility perspectives. This activity is expected to open new avenues for research and innovation, as well as to help shape sustainable business models for digital platforms. digiNEB.eu therefore aims to leverage the best practice and knowledge of the New European Bauhaus community and creates the opportunity for multidisciplinary, hands-on community collaboration towards the triple transformation in Europe.

2.4. Enable cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration

digiNEB.eu aims to connect across domains and foster interdisciplinary understanding and collaboration. One aim for the coordination action is to establish and test the idea of tools such as digital passports that will allow stakeholders to connect across domains and foster closer cooperation and monitoring of material uses in sustainable value networks. This type of cross-domain digiNEB.eu community engagement creates opportunities for greater alignment between different stakeholder groups such as primary industry, construction and architecture (see groups in 2) – all of which use different terminology and data standards. An important part of the digiNEB.eu engagement objectives is to leverage these coordination activities to gather the different stakeholders and identify gaps and opportunities for standardisation and regulation that can contribute to sustainable digitised value networks. Based on this, digiNEB.eu aims to engage European policymakers with the project's findings and policy recommendations (see KPIs list in Chapter 6).

2.5. Support continuous learning

digiNEB.eu aims to continuously support both New European Bauhaus and Smart Communities breakthroughs, novel projects and initiatives to allow for all engaged stakeholders to keep learning from each other. These include providing digital tools to assist the new NEB Academy (announced by President von der Leyen on 24 November 2022¹) and learning through digital and NEB partnerships with global communities. The digiNEB.eu project has included an External Advisory Group member from outside the EU to support the global community perspective: Sheela Patel is the founder director of the Society for Promotion of Area Resource Centres (SPARC) and an academic and activist working with people living in slums and informal accommodation in India and Bangladesh.

3. Target Stakeholder Groups

digiNEB.eu continuously engages all relevant stakeholders through communication and dissemination activities and by developing systematic and rigorous synergies and adoption programmes where it engages with its multi-stakeholder audience, including research and industry working to achieve Green Deal objectives.

Seven stakeholder groups have been selected to lead the engagement within the NEB community. Each of these groups brings their perspective, expertise, and skills to the project and will be involved in different ways. The Stakeholder Groups (SGs) have been identified to create a comprehensive network that facilitates interactions between digital and New European Bauhaus players. Details about the Engagement Plan for each SG are presented in Chapter 4. The table below provides a more detailed overview of the relevant stakeholders involved and related multiplier networks to maximise engagement.

Figure 1: Engagement of all target stakeholder groups

Active interaction with these seven selected stakeholder groups is essential for the overall success of digiNEB.eu as a community-building project. Each partner contributes by leveraging their strong networks in the international digital arena and the NEB ecosystem. As a result, for each stakeholder group, a first-hand profile and value proposition for engagement has been indicated. Furthermore, stakeholders have also been reached through relevant media channels and targeted email campaigns. The final aim is to create a comprehensive network facilitating interactions between digital and NEB

¹ The announcement was made during the conference “New European Bauhaus Goes Into the Woods” conference (<https://www.nordicbauhaus.eu/into-the-woods#/page=1>)

players. The table in Annex 1 outlines the seven stakeholder categories in more detail and the multipliers that will enable greater engagement within those categories.

4. Engagement Channels

A multi-channel approach to engagement will be implemented to reach and engage the broadly diverse target stakeholders identified in the previous section. For each dissemination & communication pathway, one or more engagement channels will be utilised.

The digiNEB.eu project is going to conduct a series of campaigns and exploit different dissemination channels, such as knowledge and matchmaking events, webinars, educational seminars and hands-on innovation labs in addition to place-based education, social media, the activation and empowerment of early adopters, as well as the digital platform itself, which provides databases, catalogues and toolkits.

The table below shows the dissemination channels that will be run throughout the project's lifetime to engage with the community.

Channel	Impact
1. digiNEB.eu Website	The collaborative Drupal-based website is the public hub of the project, with all results disseminated there. It hosts the NEB Digital observatory, Digital Toolkit of R&I results and services, the eLearning platform and online events.
2. TWGs collaborative space	The TWGs facilitate internal communication between TWG members and support collaboration with the broader community. The TWGs collaborative space is a critical engagement tool for gathering information from the community via open consultation, validating findings and disseminating recommendations.
3. NEB Digital Observatory	The Observatory maps and disseminates the projects and activities in the NEB landscape with a particular focus on R&I projects. The Observatory becomes an extra dissemination channel for projects that can manage their own project pages.
4. NEB Digital Toolkit	The NEB Digital Toolkit comprises digital tools developed by technology providers and EC-funded projects. The toolkit becomes an environment for the exploitation and sustainability of EU innovation for the NEB community, R&I projects and tech providers.
5. eLearning platform	The eLearning platform provides training programmes and material for the SGs identified. Training activities organised by projects included in the Observatory and providers in the Toolkit are also disseminated in the eLearning platform.
6. Workshops	16 workshops are delivered to disseminate NEB digital solutions, perform training activities, facilitate multi-stakeholder dialogue and ultimately close the gap between research and industry.
7. Webinars	8 webinars occur during the project to identify commonly perceived barriers and discuss how different R&I projects address them. The webinars form a core aspect identifying how current activities can shape roadmapping and policy recommendations.
8. digiNEB.eu Yearly Events	The two multi-stakeholder events serve as dissemination events for project results. Timed in M12 and M24, the first event validates results to date and

Channel	Impact
	gathers input for activities such as the Observatory and the Toolkit. The final event showcases the project results.
9. Third Party Events	Presence at events not organised primarily by digiNEB.eu is a valuable channel to raise awareness of the various solutions the project aims to roll out and find mutual ways of cooperation. The NEB Progress report published on 16 January 2023 provides a list of suitable events under section 9 where digiNEB.eu may target in the coming months. (see /2/ Section 9 References).
10. digiNEB.eu Early Adopters	The Early Adopters will act as a direct multiplier for digiNEB.eu. Their best practices highlight requirements, implementation, benefits and impact of technologies highlighted during the Early Adopters network programme.
11. External Advisory Group (EAG)	The influence the EAG members have on the project may be very significant. Each member was hand-picked at the time of the project proposal and further elaborated on at the time of Grant Agreement Preparation. Selecting those members with a NEB interest provides a more incentivised approach to contributions.
12. Publication of Results in Horizon Results platform	The primary project outcomes will be consolidated into Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to be published in the European Commission Horizon Results Platform to promote their uptake.
13. Social Media	Continuous engagement with the principal communication office at NEB headquarters allows digiNEB.eu partners to differentiate on the material produced by the project and does not double up on communicating the activities within NEB.

Table 1 - digiNEB.eu engagement pathways and impact

The following sections either describe each of the channels utilised for implementing digiNEB.eu’s Stakeholder Engagement Plan or indicate the public deliverable where such a description is included.

4.1. digiNEB.eu Website (www.digineb.eu)

The digiNEB.eu website will be the pivotal element in the engagement strategy. All channels will ultimately point at it to maximise each community member’s valuable data and ensure their continuous interaction with the NEB community.

The digiNEB.eu website is the ultimate showcase of the Landscape and Gap reports and Roadmap to highlight the current progress and plans for the deployment of digital solutions for the New European Bauhaus.

The online platform aims to act as an open, collaborative co-creation space that encourages synergies and promotes interaction and cooperation among R&I initiatives and stakeholders across Europe.

The structure and purpose of the website are described in the deliverable D2.1 (digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 1.0) and will be further presented in D5.1, “Plan for dissemination, exploitation, communication activities (DECP)”.

4.2. Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) Collaborative Space

In the following months, the digiNEB.eu platform will provide the basis for the establishment of interdisciplinary Thematic Working Groups (TWGs). The proposal uses the following topics as starting points for TWG: 1) Design & Architecture, 2) Production & Construction, 3) Verticals, and 4) Community & Sustainability. Following established NEB methods, further TWGs will be established as results of co-creation by the digiNEB.eu community and will bring together stakeholder experts and broader community contributors into the digiNEB.eu ecosystem.

Partners have agreed to replace the title “Technical Working Groups” included in the digiNEB.eu proposal with “Thematic Working Groups” (keeping the same acronym “TWG”) to ensure broader participation of the NEB community. It was agreed that organising work according to themes has greater appeal for multidisciplinary communities and can therefore lead to greater project impacts.

Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) are open to all stakeholders and form a focal point of stakeholder engagement. The TWGs will be organised around thematic areas developed with the NEB community. They will provide practical input for the 16 workshops organised in WP5 and produce a series of reports on landscape and gap analysis, best practices and other relevant topics. TWGs will also provide practical input for six networking events. Community co-creation will help evolve and shape the thematic areas listed in the digiNEB.eu proposal:

- Design & Architecture
 - Enhancing biodiversity; eco-systemic decision-making in design
 - Circular Design, design for disassembly/deconstruction
 - Morphology of human settlements: organising the relationship of urbanity and rurality
 - Architectural-data cycles for sustainable design qualities
 - Sustainable design of the rural area
 - Creative design & project environment
 - Biogenic carbon storage: designing buildings and cities as carbon banks
- Production & Construction
 - Digitising the building sector: applications throughout building and urban life cycles (online presence, VR, home automation, etc.)
 - Technologies for a sustainable construction industry
 - Engineered biomaterials and novel building products for construction
 - Additive manufacturing and CNC cutting
 - Technologies for a sustainable textiles industry & other innovative materials
 - Creative startups
- Verticals
 - Healthy living environment and buildings for health(care)
 - Education
 - Future-proof heritage
 - Existing housing stock and infrastructure
 - Building manufacturing
 - Building & mobility
- Community & Sustainability
 - People and their communities: user-centred criteria/participatory design processes for sustainable and smart urbanisation
 - Fair and just transitions: equity and empowerment for disenfranchised populations

- Biogenic carbon storage: buildings and cities as carbon banks
- Energy transition and climate adaptation in the construction industry
- Impact assessment: gathering data and tracking our footprints
- Ending waste: policies and practices in a circular construction economy

Following the announcement by President von der Leyen about the launch of the new NEB Academy, a corresponding TWG will be launched at the in-person 2.5-day workshop hosted at CERN IdeaSquare (27/02-01/03 2023). This new priority direction for NEB combines several aspects of the above TWGs: enhancing biodiversity, circularity, technologies for a sustainable construction industry, engineered biomaterials, education, participatory design processes and ending waste. Onboarding of members for the Thematic Working Groups is therefore being pursued through curated matchmaking between leading NEB contributors and digital innovation project owners. The TWGs offer an environment where ideas on these new directions can be shared and developed.

4.3. NEB Digital Observatory

digiNEB.eu’s NEB observatory includes several online features to consolidate the NEB digital ecosystem. First, the observatory aims to collate all EU-funded initiatives related to the New European Bauhaus environment to raise awareness around NEB initiatives and encourage the creation of collaborative opportunities (the so-called “best practices”).

Second, the observatory provides a shared space for digiNEB.eu to facilitate Thematic Working Group discussions. The open-source Flarum tool (www.flarum.org) will be integrated with the Drupal instance of the web platform, providing a shared space for discussion with all digiNEB.eu stakeholders. Drupal’s capability of sharing selected content exposing API endpoints allows it to reuse and show content outside the website, which aligns with the NEB initiative’s scope for openness and knowledge sharing.

Finally, the observatory includes a set of success stories linked to the digital solutions, as described below in 4.4.

Figure 2: The NEB Observatory

4.4. Success Stories

digiNEB.eu builds its work plan around showcasing success stories related to solutions listed in the NEB Digital catalogue as part of the website’s Observatory. Aside from demonstrating the potential value of the digital solutions, they also create possible synergy points among stakeholders by reinforcing and securing the digital technology supply chain.

Linking success stories to digital solutions contributes to stronger Smart Communities synergies with NEB-related projects, including the 6 successfully funded NEB Lighthouses², such as CULTUURCAMPUS, NEBourhoods, DESIRE, EHHUR, NEB-STAR and Bauhaus of the Seas Sails. These synergies allow for Smart Communities projects such as DS4SSCC focusing on clean and climate-neutral industrial value chains, circular energy-efficient buildings and cities to connect to NEB solutions for urban development, mobility, and health, such as sustainable city hubs, climate-neutral cities, climate change, biodiversity loss and energy poverty.

Featured success stories also aim to encourage dialogue with citizens on topics such as resource use, circularity methods and sustainability strategies, and create bridges between communities and experts, enhancing trust, transparency, and decision-making processes. As shown in the images below, digiNEB.eu collates and promotes success stories in its observatory section to encourage further engagement and spread best practices.

Fig. 1 – Success story header

² https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en%5E/ip_22_2780 and <https://era.gv.at/news-items/sixth-additional-new-european-bauhaus-lighthouse-demonstrator-project-funded-focusing-on-coastal-areas/>

The image shows a technical factsheet for the 'Duved Democracy Tool'. It features a grid layout with various fields and values. At the top left, there is a logo consisting of a 4x4 grid of dots in yellow and orange, followed by the title 'Technical factsheet'. Below this, the factsheet is organized into several rows and columns. The first row includes 'Date: April 2018', 'Funded', and 'EU Member state'. The second row includes 'Green dimension: Sustainable Development', 'Location: Duved, Sweden', and 'Application category: Model |'. The third row includes 'Value: SEK 500,000'. The fourth row includes 'Adopted digital solutions: Duved Democracy Tool', 'Related Technical Working Group: Community and Sustainability', and 'External Link: https://www.duvedframtid.se/english'. The fifth row includes 'Credits: © Duved Framtid AB'. At the bottom right, there is a 'Like' button with a thumbs-up icon.

Date:	April 2018	Funded	EU Member state
Green dimension	Sustainable Development	Location	Duved, Sweden
Value	SEK 500,000	Application category	Model
Adopted digital solutions	Duved Democracy Tool	Related Technical Working Group	Community and Sustainability
Credits	External Link		
© Duved Framtid AB	https://www.duvedframtid.se/english		

Figure 3: Example of a Success story technical factsheet

4.5. NEB Digital Toolkit

digiNEB.eu has worked to connect and unite the broader European NEB community by providing specific technological mechanisms and tools that will provide a useful service to existing stakeholders and early adopters and help them identify and reach out to other complementary stakeholder groups. Among these, the **NEB digital toolkit** aims to connect the digital and NEB ecosystems through dedicated areas enabling different stakeholder groups to find solutions and interact with the respective solution providers.

To this end, the project has started to assemble a toolkit of technologies that can be tested with the NEB community for the purpose of supporting the green transformation. To date, digiNEB.eu has monitored digital technology projects and outcomes supported by EU funding, specifically the results of Smart Cities and Communities programmes, and identified several suitable initiatives. The project owners of these initiatives will interact with the NEB community at the digiNEB.eu in-person event at CERN at the end of February 2023, and project partners will facilitate strong synergies to develop between these communities. We anticipate that this will lead to active Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) who can continue their discussions online.

Figure 4: NEB digital toolkit as visualised on digiNEU.eu website

Involvement strategies include one-on-one exchanges with stakeholders through private email correspondence or social media (especially LinkedIn). Moreover, thanks to its user-friendly interface, the digiNEB.eu website allows different stakeholders to add their digital solutions autonomously by subscribing to the website, creating an account, and filling in a web form. The latter undergoes an internal moderation process before it can be published to ensure that all entries are correctly entered and the text's overall quality is appropriate. After training, the moderation step can be removed for users who demonstrate proficiency. So far, around 30 solutions have been entered, and the goal is to reach 150 by the end of the project.

4.6. eLearning Platform

This platform aims to provide training programmes and material targeting the specific stakeholder groups listed in Annex 1. Moreover, training activities organised by projects included in the Observatory and providers in the Toolkit are also disseminated in the platform.

E-learning courses include a progressive 3-step iteration (M6, M12, M18) of online courses (delivered by all partners involved in the task). In addition, capacity-building material tailored to different stakeholder groups will take the form of online courses, interactive lessons, videos, compendiums and online showcase meetings where architects, designers and planners can demonstrate how their best practices can bring about actual change in the profession and meet the goals of NEB and the Green Deal.

The platform assembles existing and newly developed capacity-building material and is organised in levels (e.g., basic, intermediate, advanced). The platform will be accessible even after the project's end to continue engaging the community of NEB stakeholders.

The eLearning programme will evolve in line with the ambitions of the newly launched NEB Academy (see 2.5), and more details will be provided in two deliverables that will follow – D3.2 *Training*

programme and knowledge sharing report (M20, May 2024) and D3.3 Transferring innovation best practices (M23, August 2024).

4.7. Workshops

Workshops are physical or online events to facilitate discussions and co-creation between Smart Communities and the New European Bauhaus stakeholders.

The digiNEB.eu team plans to organise 16 hands-on co-creation workshops, often referred to as “think and do tanks”. The format is based on best practice from NEB co-creation processes and has been shown to produce greater value for the community. digiNEB.eu will facilitate clustering and convergence on common themes and challenges, foster the exchange of good practices, and identify how digital transformation can contribute to implementing digital solutions for the New European Bauhaus community projects. The workshops will be recorded, and the knowledge gathered will be distributed through dissemination and training. Six workshops will be hybrid or face-to-face, and the other ten will be entirely virtual meetings.

Figure 5: Example engagement from the 1st digiNEB.eu workshop (SCWEC, Barcelona November 2022)

Part of the strategy for greater community engagement is the leveraging of large-scale events and notable project partnerships to attract participation. One example is the Barcelona Smart Cities World Expo Congress (SCWEC), where digiNEB’s 1st workshop was organised with the NEB project CRAFT and the European Energy Research Alliance. Another example is a 2.5-day dedicated physical workshop organised in partnership with CERN and hosted at CERN IdeaSquare that will gather 50 digiNEB.eu community stakeholders. Both events will be covered in greater detail in the deliverables due in month 6 of the project.

4.8. Webinars

Webinars are central to enabling a smooth transition from physical events to virtual events and offer the chance to present the main results of the New European Bauhaus digital ecosystem.

The main strategic goals of the webinars are linked to the promotion of the digiNEB.eu and NEB main objectives: outline the main components of the digital ecosystem, recruit Early Adopters, drive forward technical discussions through the Thematic Working Groups and reinforce the cooperation established with relevant players in NEB and sustainable living spaces.

Throughout the project's lifetime, digiNEB.eu will organise eight webinars that provide a forum where the target stakeholder groups can interact with the project's team and experts in the digital and NEB ecosystem.

The 1st one, entitled "[Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus \(NEB\)](#)", took place on **12 December 2022**. The webinar was moderated by Silvana Muscella, CEO at Trust-IT srl, and showcased how digiNEB.eu can contribute to the NEB ecosystem by providing digital solutions. The event saw presentations and contributions from:

- EU representatives (Alicja Magdalena Herbowska, New European Bauhaus acting Head of Unit, Joint Research Centre and Eddy Hartog, European Commission DG Connect, Head of Unit Technologies for Smart Communities) who introduced the New European Bauhaus concept;
- experts in the construction field (Jesús Angel García Sánchez, ECTP Executive Board on Digital Built Environment) who explained the role played by the digital ecosystem in the construction industry;
- experts in the architecture and local living spaces field (Roberto Cavallo, Council member of the European Association for Architectural Education and Jan Åman, Senior Researcher at Industry Commons Foundation) who introduced the Early Adopters programme and the Duved model;
- experts in the NEB and digital ecosystem (Michela Magas, Chair at Industry Commons Foundation and member of the NEB High-level roundtable; and Ruth Schagemann, President of the Architects' Council of Europe (ACE)) who joined a panel discussion aimed at showcasing how the NEB principles, and in particular the use of digital solutions for NEB, facilitate this mindset shift and accelerate the transition to climate-neutral cities to make them more inclusive, sustainable and beautiful.

The webinar provided an engaging forum to present the Duved model for local communities. Duved provides a case study of a sustainable rural and civil engineering governance approach through local cooperation and, as such, provides a thematic focus that draws together and connects a wide range of stakeholders from different knowledge domains and societal sectors. It has also been offered as a physical hub for prototyping, circular strategies and place-based education for the digiNEB.eu project.

The webinar represented a relevant event for all stakeholder groups showcased in Section 2, as shown in the Figure below.

Figure 6: Stakeholder engagement impact from the first webinar

The 2nd webinar is scheduled for **14 February**, focusing more strongly on blockchain technology. The webinar features the Max Planck Digital Library project Bloxberg, which is organising the event with digiNEB.eu. The webinar provides the opportunity to learn more about a trusted decentralised network for the blockchain registration of scientific research developed by Bloxberg and how this solution helps manage intellectual property in creative and cultural environments.

4.9. digiNEB.eu Yearly Events

In addition to the organisation of webinars and workshops, the digiNEB.eu consortium will run two yearly events in M12 and M24 to increase the engagement level with identified SGs.

The two multi-stakeholder events serve as dissemination events for project results. The first event validates results to date and facilitates discussions to gather inputs for ongoing activities, such as digital solutions to be added to the Digital Toolkit, success stories for the Observatory or relevant insights for the digiNEB.eu Roadmap.

The second and final event showcases the project's main results of the digiNEB.eu.

Both events are open to the public and will be divided into sessions where each attendee can learn more and contribute to specific topics connected to the digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus.

4.10. Third-Party Events

Third-party events help digiNEB.eu to gain visibility, communicate benefits for target audiences, gain insights into the latest digital innovations to support the NEB community and make new contacts as part of the community development.

Participation includes presentations, panel debates, promotional stands, poster displays, remote participation and the distribution of project promotional material (roll-up banners, fliers, etc.) for focused and effective engagement outcomes, with live reporting via Twitter, updates on Instagram

and articles on LinkedIn. Third-party events are selected for their timeliness with digiNEB.eu outputs, topic and audience relevance.

The digiNEB.eu team tracks the number and impact of each 3rd-party event attended in an online shared document, and the public ones are also published on the digiNEB.eu website.

The list of 3rd-party events attended by the digiNEB.eu consortium in the period M01 – M04 is summarised in the table below.

Nr.	Event name	Type of event	Organised by	Event Dates	Location	digiNEB.eu partner to attend	Private or public workshop	Target SGs	Impact
1	EC Bioeconomy	Workshop	Wood4Bauhaus Alliance	6 – 7 October 2022	Brussels (BE)	Uwe Kies (IW)	Public	SG1, SG2, SG3, SG4, SG5, SG6, SG7	Visibility for digiNEB.eu to the Wood4Bauhaus Alliance, EC bioeconomy conference participants and nature-based solutions network community. 120 attendants (online and physically at the European Commission).
2	European Week of Regions and Cities	Workshop	EC Commission	10 – 13 October 2022	Brussels (BE)	Michela Magas (ICF)	Public	SG5, SG6, SG7	Visibility for digiNEB.eu to European local policymakers
3	NEB Day – Aveiro Tech Week	Workshop	City of Aveiro	10 – 16 October 2022	Aveiro (PT)	Michela Magas (ICF)	Public	SG5, SG6, SG7	Visibility for digiNEB.eu to European artists and digital players
4	Architectural Education in Times of Uncertainty Symposium	Symposium	TU Delft	2 – 4 November 2022	Delft (NL)	Roberto Cavallo, Mar Munoz Aparici (EAAE)	Private	SG1, SG2, SG3, SG5, SG6	Scouting of 5 training courses to be added to the eLearning
5	Barcelona Smart City Expo	Panel discussion	FIRA Barcelona	15 – 17 November 2022	Barcelona (ES)	Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT)	Public	SG1, SG2, SG3, SG4, SG5, SG6, SG7	Visibility for digiNEB.eu to digital industrial players, policymakers, architects, engineers and citizens Connection established with 30+ digital players willing to showcase their solutions on the Digital Toolkit Connection with 10+ EU-funded initiatives, willing to showcase their outputs as success stories in the

Nr.	Event name	Type of event	Organised by	Event Dates	Location	digiNEB.eu partner to attend	Private or public workshop	Target SGs	Impact
									Observatory and their digital solutions in the Digital Toolkit
6	ICC Mayors Forum and ICC Conference	Conference	ICC	16 November 2022	Barcelona (ES)	Michela Magas (ICF)	Public	SG5, SG6, SG7	Visibility for digiNEB.eu to European local policymakers and citizens
7	OASC Connected Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities Conference	Conference	OASC	17 – 18 January 2023	Brussels (BE)	Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT)	Public	SG1, SG2, SG3, SG4, SG5, SG6, SG7	Visibility for digiNEB.eu to architects and local policymakers Engagement with 8 local government representatives willing to share details on the digital solutions adopted in their cities as success stories in the Observatory
8	Transforming The Built Environment	Workshop	Chalmers University of Technology	16 – 18 January 2023	Gothenburg (SE)	Michela Magas (ICF)	Private	SG5, SG6, SG7	Visibility for digiNEB.eu to researchers and policymakers
9	CCSI event	Conference	Swedish Presidency of the Council of the EU	16 – 17 February 2023	Umeå (SE)	Michela Magas (ICF)	Private	SG5, SG6, SG7	Visibility for digiNEB.eu to policymakers and local government representatives
10	Impact of care	Workshop	EAAE / KU Leuven	20 – 21 April 2023	Brussels (BE)	Roberto Cavallo (EAAE)	Public	SG3	Visibility for digiNEB.eu to research and academia

Table 2 – 3rd-party events attended by the digiNEB.eu partners in the period M01-M06

4.11. digiNEB.eu Early Adopters

digiNEB.eu will leverage the interest and engagement of early adopters of the digiNEB.eu platform for further outreach. The digiNEB.eu Early Adopters are champions who use digital solutions and so act as ambassadors or enthusiastic mediators between the creators of the tools and their own wider communities. Such champions help community-building processes by facilitating community interaction and onboarding broader communities.

The Early Adopter programme provides a win-win situation since, aside from helping build the digiNEB.eu community, early adopters will receive visibility at a local and EU level to showcase their best practices to the NEB community, receiving recognition that can be directly referenced and linked to (for instance, from their website or on a Wikipedia page) and be invited to present at digiNEB.eu webinars. Selected content chosen by early adopters will also be made available (under granted & referenced permission), promoted and highlighted on the digiNEB.eu platform as a reference for the digiNEB.eu community.

As part of the engagement strategy, an application form has been uploaded on the website, explaining what an early adopter is and requesting to enter basic personal information and motivation to become an early adopter.

Become one of the future digiNEB.eu Early Adopters

You will act as one of our main Ambassadors by:

- telling your story of utilising digital solutions in your NEB-related projects;
- identifying gaps in the NEB digital ecosystem and helping find solutions to address them;
- gaining visibility at local and/or international events;
- shaping and transferring innovation best practices;

Be a digiNEB.eu ambassador and gain distinguished visibility within the NEB community!

Name*

Surname*

Email*

What describes you best?*

Tell us why you want to become an early adopter*

I accept digiNEB.eu's [privacy policy](#) and [terms of use](#)*
For information about our privacy practices, visit our privacy policy page.

APPLY

Figure 7: Early Adopters Webform posted on digiNEB.eu website

4.12. External Advisory Group

The External Advisory Group connects digiNEB.eu with proactive, eminent stakeholders with thought leadership and influence. The EAG was established as one of the project's outcomes to provide competent and independent guidance to the project while at the same time supporting both thematic working groups and the NEB catalogue through roadmap recommendations. These advisors can provide the project with timely knowledge (technical, policy and innovation) to support content and outputs (i.e., roadmap, policy briefs, TWG reports) and impact policy, industry and research.

The EAG offers guidance to the project results published on the project website and is made of prominent experts in relevant areas for the project, with complementary backgrounds across creative industries, accessibility, architecture, design and construction materials. It comprises 16 renowned and esteemed EAG members (eight women and eight men) who have agreed to bring their expertise to the digiNEB.eu community. Below is a complete list of the External Advisory Group members:

Michela Magas (Chair), Partner digiNEB.eu Industry Commons Foundation

- **Christina Claesson-Jonsson**, Director of Research and Development at NCC AB, construction industry
- **Annette Hafner**, Professor at Ruhr-Universität Bochum
- **Selma Harrington**, Executive Board Member at The Architects' Council of Europe (ACE)
- **Dimitris Kiritsis**, Professor of ICT and Sustainable Manufacturing at EPFL (École Polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne)
- **Matti Kuittinen**, Senior Ministerial Advisor at the Ministry of the Environment of Finland
- **Andreja Kutnar**, Director at InnoRenew CoE
- **Martin Luce**, Director at TUM School of Engineering and Design
- **Tom Minderhoud**, Sensor Architect at UNStudio
- **Kirsi Mustalahti**, Founder & Chairwoman at ACCAC Global
- **Fredrik Nilsson**, Professor, Vice President of Campus and Sustainable Development at Chalmers University of Technology
- **Alan Organschi**, Director at Bauhaus Earth
- **Sheela Patel**, Grassroots Global Activist at International Institute for Environment and Development
- **Ignasi Pérez Arnal**, Director at REBUILD Congress
- **Francesca Rizzo**, Full Professor at Politecnico di Milano
- **Mia Roth-Čerina**, Vice-Dean for International Relations and Art at the University of Zagreb
- **Ruth Schagemann**, President of the Architects' Council of Europe (ACE-CAE)
- **Jose Pedro Sousa**, Associate Professor at the University of Porto.

As shown in the list above, each individual has been selected from diverse organisations and research institutions to cater for a broad domain range and balanced geographical distribution. Experts were chosen for their experience and roles as advisors or experts in sectoral innovation, market needs, government policies and societal impact. They reflect the different NEB stakeholders and include experts in architecture, accessibility, construction, design, engineering, and national and regional policy. EAG members have affiliations with prestigious institutions, including Yale University, the Architect's Council of Europe, and the Ministry of the Environment of Finland. They have been selected to ensure a comprehensive representation of the Stakeholder Groups and create fundamental synergistic relationships with external institutions and organisations to facilitate the learning & transfer process.

Figure 8: digiNEB.eu External Advisory Group comprises multidisciplinary experts from Sweden, Germany, Switzerland, Finland, Slovenia, Croatia, Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Portugal and India.

4.13. NEB community and NEB Academy

The digiNEB.eu team has established a good working relationship and continuous dialogue with the NEB communication team to ensure that the digiNEB.eu communication strategy is aligned with that of the New European Bauhaus. The digiNEB.eu and NEB teams communicate via emails or video calls and present the main topics to be carried out in the next month, summarised in a collaborative online document. The cooperation between digiNEB.eu and the NEB team helps each to multiply the impacts of their work and reach a wider audience.

More information on the communication flow between digiNEB.eu and NEB will be described in the deliverable *D5.1 Plan for dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities (DECP)* due in month 6.

The main digiNEB.eu goal is to develop the digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus, which, as discussed above, comprises:

- **Digital Toolkit:** a catalogue with over 200 digital solutions for the NEB ecosystem;
- **Observatory:** a collection of 500 EU-funded initiatives and success stories to raise awareness of NEB programmes and the benefits of digital solutions, as well as to encourage collaborations;
- **eLearning catalogue:** a collaborative online set of courses and training materials aimed at stimulating knowledge and sharing best practices.

As presented in paragraphs **3.5 NEB Digital Toolkit**, **3.6 Success Stories** and **3.7 Thematic Working Groups**, the Digital Toolkit and Observatory were already successfully launched by December 2022 and are accessible through the digiNEB.eu website.

The eLearning catalogue will be launched by March 2023. It will provide the context for the development of the conceptual foundation and first version of a Learning Content Management System (LCMS) that can integrate with elements of the NEB Academy. The LCMS presents technical solutions in the form of a catalogue of courses and user guidelines provided by authors willing to share their knowledge with NEB and digiNEB.eu. The topics included in the NEB Academy platform include sustainable wood and forestry construction, and bio-based materials programmes.

To engage with the community and increase awareness about the eLearning Courses and the NEB academy, digiNEB.eu intends to implement the following engagement strategies:

1. Of the 16 workshops to be conducted by the digiNEB.eu project, several will be dedicated to or include the **NEB Academy STG**. Dedicated NEB Academy workshops will be designed and carried out as part of **Task 5.2 Events Management**, subject to approval by the EC NEB Team and with an agenda to be coordinated in collaboration with them. The workshops will be “powered by digiNEB.eu” and will be upskilling events that are coordination opportunities deploying a digital toolkit of solutions to communities in a collaborative and stimulating context. Synergies will be pursued so the NEB Lighthouse projects, NEB partners and Friends of NEB can host the workshops.
2. Activation of a **Thematic Working Group** focused primarily on the NEB Academy is planned for the second in-person event hosted by CERN IdeaSquare (27/02-01/03 2023) and will shape the needs, gaps and recommendations for the NEB Academy.
3. The **Digital Toolkit** can serve as a valuable resource for academy members and trainees to find digital solutions essential for any academic development and curricula envisaged by the academy.

digiNEB.eu will identify and liaise with New European Bauhaus initiatives, NEB partners and NEB Lighthouse projects on the development of the NEB Academy. The project will invite existing groups already connected with New European Bauhaus activities to use the platform to gather, connect and share knowledge. The role that digiNEB.eu will play with respect to the NEB Academy will be further defined during the in-person event at CERN.

4.14. Social media

digiNEB.eu aims to amplify and promote the above engagement channels and strategies through relevant social media channels. Since the project's launch, social media have been used to consolidate the digiNEB.eu online presence, communicate outputs and engage with target Stakeholder Groups (SGs).

digiNEB.eu is present on four social media channels:

- **Instagram:** the primary means of communication for the NEB community due to the strong use of imagery and aesthetics. DigiNEB.eu uses Instagram to promote collaborative projects and results using visual imagery.
- **Twitter:** the account @digineb is the channel mainly used for quick and general communication about the project and is frequently updated through captivating visuals and to-the-point messaging to reach communities and policymakers since NEB notably does not have a Twitter channel.
- **LinkedIn:** LinkedIn has recently been added to the list of NEB communication channels. For digiNEB, LinkedIn will be used both to align with NEB and engage architects, designers, engineers, business professionals and researchers.
- **YouTube:** the channel is used to host three main types of content, which can then also be reused on other platforms via sharing or embedding:
 - Interviews
 - Recordings of webinars or other events
 - Tutorials and explanation videos

To monitor the impact and engagement level of the SGs through social media channels, the Trust-IT team runs SMART campaigns, which are Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic, and Time-bound. Campaigns each have specific launch, mid-term and end dates to monitor performance throughout their lifespan. Campaigns are used to promote demo videos, webinars, workshops, and digiNEB.eu

attendance at 3rd-party events to maximise reach and impact through social media. The deliverable **D5.1 Plan for dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities (DECP)** will provide more details on the result of each social media campaign.

5. Stakeholder Engagement Plan

The present Stakeholder Engagement Plan includes all activities that the digiNEB.eu consortium aims to implement in its lifetime to connect with identified SGs and ensure their interaction is mutually beneficial.

Engagement with stakeholders will be an activity that involves all members of the digiNEB.eu consortium. Partners will each contribute to upskilling, upscaling and leveraging existing projects. Linking with partners' existing networks and connections will be an essential aspect of this outreach, as well as ensuring that digital divide and data literacy issues are addressed within stakeholder-specific domains. In addition, each partner will have a specific focal area, in part to share the workload and leverage key strengths but also to avoid duplication.

The role played by each partner is summarised in the table below:

Partner name	Engagement role and responsibility
Delft University of Technology (TU Delft)	The partner is the primary contact for creating the digiNEB.eu Thematic Working Groups. TU Delft will provide, as the main outcome, the development of landscape and gap reports and contribution to the strategic digiNEB.eu Deployment Roadmap. Furthermore, TU Delft is engaged in three NEB Lighthouse projects (CULTUURCAMPUS, NEB-STAR, and DESIRE), ensuring a smooth dialogue with them.
Trust-IT srl (Trust-IT)	The partner is the main contact for the organisation of webinars and workshops aimed at showcasing the potential of digital solutions for NEB and the training academy. Trust-IT is also responsible for creating strong synergies with digiNEB.eu sister projects (e.g. DS4SSCC, Living in EU) or any other initiative connected to sustainable living spaces.
COMMpla srl (COMMpla)	The partner is the primary developer of the NEB digital platform, which includes the Digital Toolkit, Observatory and eLearning Platform.
Industry Commons Foundation (ICF)	Given the strong connection to the NEB High-Level Round Table played by ICF, the partner creates strong synergies and engagement with the NEB-related projects (e.g. NEB Lighthouse projects, Friends of the NEB). Moreover, ICF brings together an extensive network of 8,000 creative innovators and experts in cross-domain collaboration. Chair Michela Magas is a member of President von der Leyen's High Level Round Table for NEB, the members of which each has their own extensive networks of stakeholders and potential users of the digiNEB.eu platform.
European Association for Architectural Education (EAAE)	EAAE is one of the main contributors to scout and recruit Early Adopters of the NEB Digital Ecosystem. The team also contributes to adding relevant content for the eLearning courses included in the NEB Academy.
InnovaWood (IW)	The partner has a strong experience in NEB-related initiatives connected to sustainable wood and forestry construction and bio-based materials and acts as one of the leading players in creating engagement towards the stakeholders involved in this field. Moreover, InnovaWood will be instrumental in seeking training and digital solutions related to the forestry industry.

Table 4 - Engagement roles and responsibilities played by the digiNEB.eu consortium

The coordination among all the partners involved is ensured via periodic meetings. The coordination ensures the implementation of a dedicated plan, differentiated by Stakeholder Group, as presented in the paragraphs below.

5.1. Plan and Timeline

The digiNEB.eu consortium will perform dedicated campaigns to support the building of an engaged community through four distinct phases, as described during the proposal phase.

Figure 7: Campaigns and channels to engage with the stakeholders

Currently, the project team is in the first phase [M1-M6] DEVELOP phase and has already achieved the majority of goals set up for the first six months:

DEVELOP phase activities	Status at M03	Means of verification
digiNEB.eu platform v1 online	The platform was launched in M01.	Platform available at https://digiNEB.eu/
Set-up and recruitment of TWGs	The TWGs discussion forums were set up in M02 on the Observatory, and the recruitment of experts is in progress.	TWGs discussion forums accessible at https://digiNEB.eu/observatory The outcomes of the TWGs meetings will be collected in deliverable D2.3 (Landscape report and gap analysis – preliminary version)
Definition and development of Observatory, Toolkit and eLearning platform	The Toolkit was launched in M02, and the Observatory in M03. The eLearning platform will be launched in M06.	Toolkit available at https://digiNEB.eu/digital-toolkit Observatory available at https://digiNEB.eu/observatory
Communication channels set-up (social media, newsletter etc.)	All communication channels have been set up from M01.	LinkedIn account: https://www.linkedin.com/company/digiNEB Twitter account: https://twitter.com/digiNEB Instagram account: https://www.instagram.com/digiNEB_eu YouTube account: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCxdMCusZsPidTGhg6ve6ImQ

DEVELOP phase activities	Status at M03	Means of verification
		Newsletter: https://digiNEB.eu/news-digest Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=digiNEB
4 multi-stakeholder workshops in first 6 months (16 in total)	The 1st workshop was organised in November 2022, and the 2nd one will be held in February and March 2023. The other two workshops will be arranged with the TWGs between April and May 2023.	All workshops are published at https://digiNEB.eu/events
2 webinars	The 1st webinar was organised in M03, and the 2nd one will be organised in M05.	All webinars are published at https://digiNEB.eu/events

Table 5 - Develop phase status

5.2. 5.2 Engagement actions for each Stakeholder Group

To ensure that each SG is interested in contributing to shaping the NEB digital ecosystem and can benefit from the digiNEB.eu outcomes, the consortium has started a plan to maximise the engagement per stakeholder, as shown in the Figure below. This plan will be amplified following greater stakeholder engagement and through alignment with the NEB initiative.

Stakeholder Group	Categories	Engagement Plan
SG#1	Architects, Designers, Engineers, and other professionals belonging to the NEB community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Joining the Early Adopters programme to showcase digital solutions adopted by the ● Becoming active users of the Digital Toolkit and Observatory ● Upskilling knowledge and skills thanks to access to the NEB Academy and eLearning courses ● Contributing to TWG discussion groups and accessing Landscape and Gap reports as the main outcome of TWG ● Participating in webinars and workshops to better understand the main goals and strategies of the NEB digital ecosystem
SG#2	Construction industry suppliers & other relevant industry players, including start-ups, SMEs, associations in the building, mobility & health sectors, and SDOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Receiving exposure by providing digital solutions that will populate the Digital Toolkit and can become potential Success Stories ● Getting access to the NEB digital ecosystem to better understand the solutions offered by other suppliers in the market ● Upskilling knowledge and skills thanks to access to the NEB Academy and eLearning courses ● Contributing to TWG discussion groups and accessing Landscape and Gap reports as the primary outcome of TWG

Stakeholder Group	Categories	Engagement Plan
SG#3	Research and academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lowering the knowledge gap by providing learning resources and accessing the ones collected through the eLearning platform ● Contributing to TWG discussion groups and accessing Landscape and Gap reports as the main outcome of TWG ● Providing access to digital solutions developed in the scope of R&I initiatives and EU-funded projects ● Participating in webinars and workshops to contribute to shaping the future needs of the NEB digital ecosystem
SG#4	Digital technology companies & associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Receiving exposure by providing digital solutions that will populate the Digital Toolkit and can become potential Success Stories ● Getting access to the NEB digital ecosystem to better understand the solutions offered in the market ● Participating in webinars and workshops to contribute to shaping the future needs of the NEB digital ecosystem ● Upskilling knowledge and skills thanks to access to the NEB Academy and eLearning courses
SG#5	Policy Makers, including Green Deal-related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Accessing Landscape and Gap reports and Roadmap as a basis to shape future policies for digital NEB environments at the European level ● Participating in webinars and workshops to contribute to providing insights from European policy viewpoints
SG#6	National & regional authorities, mayors (including urban planners) and cities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing success stories and digital solutions successfully implemented in cities and villages ● Accessing Landscape and Gap reports and Roadmap as a basis to shape future policies for digital NEB environments at the local level ● Participating in webinars and workshops to contribute to providing insights from local policy viewpoints
SG#7	Civil society organisations and citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participating in webinars to better understand the goals of digiNEB.eu and the New European Bauhaus to learn how citizens can contribute to making an impact ● Accessing the resources collected in the eLearning catalogue to lower knowledge gaps

Table 6 - Engagement plan per Stakeholder Group

6. Synergies

Sharing the benefits of developing the NEB Digital Ecosystem is a collaborative activity. Since the beginning of digiNEB, the project team has established strong synergies with initiatives in the NEB and built environment domains to foster the adoption of digitalisation to create more inclusive, sustainable and beautiful living spaces.

The following represents the types of initiatives digiNEB.eu aims to engage with, and the main achievements gathered in the first three months from its launch.

6.1. NEB Lighthouse project

The NEB [Lighthouse projects](#) are demonstrators that can showcase the benefits and practicalities of applying the NEB's main goals locally. To date, the following 6 Lighthouse projects have been selected³:

CULTUURCAMPUS: A sustainable hub of arts, research, learning and community as a catalyst. By blending education, research, policy, and culture and considering the lived experiences of its residents, Cultuurcampus aims to transform the disadvantaged urban area of Rotterdam South (NL). The Cultuurcampus will be in a historic building and act as a hub for different groups and activities. (<https://www.cultuurencampusrotterdam.nl/en/>)

NEB-STAR (New European Bauhaus STAvanger): NEB-STAR will showcase how territorial transformation plans can incorporate the principles and values of the NEB in Stavanger (NO), Prague (CZ) and Utrecht (NL). The project will tackle four emblematic challenges linked to climate-neutral cities, all considering local needs and concerns through co-creation with residents and stakeholders. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079952>)

NEBourhoods: NEBourhoods prepares Munich-Neuperlach (DE) for the future as mapped out by the European Green Deal regarding the built environment, circularity, mobility, energy, food, and health. The project will build on the area's strengths – a strong sense of community, vast green areas, and large-scale housing, even if in need of renovation – and address its weaknesses – higher than average unemployment and lower than average education levels. (<https://www.nebourhoods.de/>)

DESIRE (Designing the Irresistible Circular Society): the project wants to tackle the major challenges faced by societies and cities: climate change, biodiversity loss and resource challenges. Based on three main themes of inclusivity, circularity and reconciling cities with nature, the project will use art, architecture, and design to explore alternative ways of transforming territories across different European cities in Denmark, the Netherlands, Italy, Latvia and Slovenia. (<https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu/>)

EHHUR (EYES HEARTS HANDS Urban Revolution): the project supports cities and vulnerable residents in transforming their built environment. Spread across seven different locations in the EU and Associated Countries (Denmark, Belgium, Portugal, Italy, Greece, Turkey, and Croatia), it will seek to tackle socioeconomic and cultural challenges such as social segregation, energy poverty, and degradation of depopulated historical centres. (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079948>)

Bauhaus of the Seas: the project aims to promote renewed ethical and aesthetic regenerative development from a diverse range of dimensions of our continued relationship with the sea.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_2780

Conceived as a journey with Portugal as a starting point, the Bauhaus of the Seas will generate a design movement extending to all European coastal and maritime regions.

The NEB Lighthouse projects will be engaged through dedicated workshops where the experts can bring their own experiences in cities, regions and nations to help implement the NEB principles thanks to digitalisation. The aim of the synergies will be that, in turn, the lighthouse projects may utilise the various digiNEB.eu solutions to increase impact.

6.2. digiNEB.eu and sister CSA projects

digiNEB.eu started to engage with projects that share similarities in terms of communities and objectives in October 2022.

The two sister projects, which are CSAs, are DS4SSCC and Living in EU:

- [DS4SSCC](#) (Data Space for Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities) is an EU-funded initiative that prepares for the creation of a data space for smart communities as an enabler of the EU Green Deal goals and Sustainable Development Goals.
- [Living in EU](#): through co-creation with citizens, the project aims to bring the economic and social benefits of this transformation to all local communities and implement an inclusive digital Europe with powerful digital services, technologies, infrastructures and skills).

The three projects have established a collaboration task force in which the coordinators of the initiatives meet monthly to discuss synergies and cooperation activities. The main discussion points from the meeting are summarised in the minutes and actions to be delivered for the next meeting.

A cluster review for our EU projects dealing with Technologies for Smart Cities and Communities is scheduled for early June 2023. It aims to be a useful activity to share results and collaborations. Currently, the projects cooperate by co-organising workshops and events and helping in dissemination and communication activities.

6.3. NEB-oriented and sustainable living spaces projects

In addition to the abovementioned synergies, the digiNEB.eu consortium will establish synergies with stakeholders involved in NEB-oriented initiatives, such as [NEB Goes South](#), the [New European Bauhaus of the Mountains](#), [Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus](#), the [Friends of NEB](#), the [NEB High Level Round Table](#), and NEB Labs across all of the EU cities and regions, leveraging the already extensive networks within those frameworks. Cooperation with these initiatives will include the organisation of co-creation events that lead to high-level recommendations for developing the Deployment Roadmap. The work undertaken by these initiatives can also be showcased as a success story on the NEB Observatory.

A synergy with the Nordic Bauhaus was already envisaged in November 2022: Nordic Bauhaus ran an event called *Bauhaus Goes To The Woods*⁴ on 24 November 2022 that drew in wood producers, forestry and primary industry, environmental scientists, open data specialists, ministers and policymakers in countries for whom wood production is extremely important, as well as architects and construction firms with a particular interest in wood construction. By organising around topics of interest rather than industry specialism, the event was able to be much more inclusive. **digiNEB.eu will use thematic and mission-driven approaches to gather multidisciplinary communities that converge around specific shared missions.** Rather than simply gathering the members of the textiles industry, a textiles theme will draw in various stakeholders interested in that domain that may not have been considered otherwise or who use textiles in a range of different applications – such as the

⁴ <https://www.nordicbauhaus.eu/into-the-woods#/page=1>

aeronautics industry. By organising engagement channels around missions and topics such as textiles, digiNEB.eu can more closely align with the NEB principles of openness, inclusion and multidisciplinary.

Lists, such as the one above, are unavoidably exclusive, so digiNEB.eu will focus on open, inclusive targets that include existing NEB initiatives such as *Nordic Bauhaus*, the community-led NEB Lab project *Carbon Free Bauhaus*, *Bauhaus Goes South* and their stakeholder groups. digiNEB.eu has on its External Advisory Group (EAG) Matti Kuittinen, a representative of the Finnish Ministry of the Environment and Chair of the Nordic Bauhaus, and Professor José Pedro Sousa of *Bauhaus Goes South*, both of which have extensive networks of their own.

In addition, the digiNEB.eu consortium aims to establish synergies with projects that operate in the local living spaces and digital environments, such as:

- [AURORAL](#): Architecture for Unified Regional and Open digital ecosystems for Smart Communities and Rural Areas Large scale applications.
- [DUET](#): Virtual city replicas that make it easy to understand the complex interrelation between traffic, air quality, noise and other urban factors. Powerful analytics model the expected impacts of potential change to aid evidence-based operational decisions and longer-term policy choices.
- [CommunityCity](#): A transformative citizen-centred project that will launch 100 tech pilots addressing the needs of cities and communities through co-creation and co-learning processes.
- [CrAft](#): Part of the New European Bauhaus initiative that will place the transition to climate neutrality at the heart of urban stakeholders. The project supports the Mission Board on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and the NetZeroCities platform in designing and deploying Climate City Contracts based on knowledge from CrAft's 3 Sandbox Cities (Bologna, Prague, and Amsterdam) and 60 CrAft Reference Cities.

Connections with these projects have been established through 3rd-party events joined by the digiNEB.eu team (Barcelona Smart City Expo and OASC Connected Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities Conference). The cooperation will span from organising events to sharing digital solutions that will be added to the Digital Toolkit of success stories in the Observatory.

6.4. Multipliers

The Multiplier network is showcased in Annex 1 Stakeholder groups and multiplier network.

Chapter 2 above lists highly relevant initiatives that are exploited to multiply the effects of the engagement process with the final aim of creating a comprehensive network facilitating interactions between digital and NEB players.

7. Monitoring

The impact of all strategically important digiNEB.eu activities performed is measured through a core set of key performance indicators (KPIs) wherever they are quantifiable. Continuous monitoring activity is carried out by Trust-IT as the T4.3 task leader and shared with all partners.

7.1. KPIs

Qualitative metrics come into play whenever there is a need for a deeper analysis of the relevance of outcomes achieved. The table below shows the end-of-project KPI targets and their status at M03.

To tangibly monitor the impact of the digiNEB.eu activities, an online Dashboard will be created by M06 and continuously updated, including all relevant KPIs mapped by the digiNEB.eu project.

While only in the project's month 3 (M03), many KPIs are already trackable and appear in line with the final month's objectives (M24). However, not all are currently trackable, as some activities have not started yet.

KPI Number	Description	Status at M03	KPI at M24
1	F2F General Meetings	1	5
2	EAG members engaged	14	10
3	EAG strategic meetings	1	2
4	Digital solutions mapped and part of the digiNEB.eu Toolkit	27	250
5	Digital solutions TWG1 - Design and Architecture	N/A (available from Sept 2023)	50
6	Digital solutions TWG2 - Production and Construction	N/A (available from Sept 2023)	50
7	Digital solutions TWG3 - Verticals	N/A (available from Sept 2023)	50
8	Digital solutions TWG4 - Community and Sustainability	N/A (available from Sept 2023)	50
9	Open licenses (e.g. MIT) with existing projects	0	25
10	TWGs	N/A (the establishment is in progress)	4
11	Projects/initiatives in the Observatory	2	500
12	Policy briefs by TWGs	N/A (available from Sept 2023)	4
13	Gap & Landscape Analysis report	N/A (available from Sept 2023)	4
14	Trainees	N/A (eLearning platform from March 2023)	1000
15	Unique visitors to digineb.eu (cumulative)	1131	50000
16	Website Iteration	1	3
17	Early Adopters	N/A (start Jan 2023)	100
18	Synergies created	9	100
19	Stakeholder database (incl social media)	594	3000
20	Newsletters (sent out)	2	21
21	Users engaged at events	149	2000
22	Videos	10	24
23	Social media content items published on socials (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram)	85	192
24	Social media followers (total all channels)	362	7000
25	Visualisation of videos (cumulative)	714	120000
26	Webinars organised (100 attendees each)	1	8
27	Workshops organised (50 attendees each)	1	16
28	Yearly events organised (150 attendees each)	N/A (1st one in Sept 2023)	2

29	NEB Roadmap	N/A (available in Sept 2023)	1
30	Marketing Campaigns	1	6
31	Attended external events	8	not set

Table 7 - digiNEB.eu KPIs

7.2. Website monitoring

All website analytical data is gathered continuously using **Google Analytics** and will be monitored weekly using a custom **Google Data Studio** dashboard to derive detailed statistics about online engagement. Monitoring will be in place to track the project KPIs related to website performance, proactively detect possible problems, and implement corrective actions. The Google Analytics profile was set up in M1, and the first data about traffic sources, visitors, navigation paths and conversions are being tracked. The primary data will be disclosed in the upcoming dissemination deliverables. Dynamic engagement strategies will respond to real-time online metrics. Project update reports will be collected as a more statistically significant data source as traffic grows due to upcoming communication and engagement activities.

A traffic KPI has been set for the activities in WP4 that will be measured with Google Analytics:

- Traffic: # sessions per month >1.5k at M12, >5k at M24;

The traffic KPI (# of sessions) will be pursued with close cooperation with the communication activities in WP5. As an example of such collaboration, a set of different copy templates for social media posts can be tested to assess which format is more attractive, thus resulting in more traffic.

Other relevant metrics, even if not set as KPIs, will be monitored to assess the success of the operation: individual logins, session duration, number and frequency of new vs returning users, conversion actions (e.g., submitting a web form or downloading a pdf), etc. These, in turn, will help achieve the communication target KPI by helping the communication teams focus on activities that are not only designed to increase traffic but also ensure social media visits.

Similarly, traffic sources, visitor geographies, most viewed pages, etc., are breakdown dimensions that will help us understand which parts of the NEB digital hub are being actively visited and which are not in terms of traffic acquisition and content generation.

A customised dashboard depicting our Google Analytics results has been set up to monitor these breakdown dimensions and will be updated monthly until M24 (September 2024). In the snapshot below, examples of such metrics and dimensions are shown:

Fig.9 Snapshot of digiNEB.eu Google Analytics

Future versions of the dashboard will include and monitor variables such as the adoption of digital tools and all other relevant KPIs identified by all WPs. The adoption growth will be marked in a benchmarking activity assessing hands-on engagement and adoption of digital tools in a blended environment that will include technology providers. User feedback will be collected, and all input will be processed and reverted to the various WPs for iteration and channelling towards further deployment and benchmarking activities. Finally, the successful deployment of technologies will be assessed in a series of feedback loops.

7.3. Other impact monitoring

Throughout the digiNEB.eu lifecycle, the project team is going to evaluate the impact of all the engagement activities performed:

Engagement Activity	Description	Impact by M03
Organisation of webinars, workshops, yearly events and participation in 3rd-party events	The organisation and participation in events help digiNEB.eu give visibility to the NEB Digital Ecosystem to all identified SG categories.	The project has reached 149 stakeholders through the webinar and 10,000+ people through third-party events
Development of the Community Database	The Community Database collects all stakeholders digiNEB.eu has engaged with through social media channels, newsletters or online and physical events.	594 people (362 are coming from social media)
Establishment of TWGs	The TWGs bring together top-class experts of the NEB digital ecosystem to stimulate discussions and share best practices that are collected to provide strategic policy recommendations.	The identification of the TWGs experts is in progress, and their work will generate four landscape reports and contributions to the two iterations of the digiNEB.eu Roadmap
Establishment of synergies	Establishment of strong synergies with initiatives in the NEB and local living spaces area to foster the adoption of digitalisation to build more inclusive, sustainable and beautiful living spaces.	The dialogue to clarify the scope of collaboration has started with nine synergies
Development of the Digital Toolkit	The NEB Digital Toolkit comprises digital tools developed by technology providers and EC-funded projects.	27 Digital Solutions added.
Development of the Observatory	The Observatory maps and disseminates the projects and activities in the NEB landscape with a particular focus on R&I projects. It comprises success stories, TWG discussions, and Early Adopters' stories and events.	15 items added, of which: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 success stories - 4 TWG discussion groups - 8 events
Development of the eLearning catalogue	Collaborative online catalogue of initiatives and digital solutions that include best practices and training materials. The eLearning courses stimulate knowledge sharing and are freely accessible on the digiNEB.eu platform.	The impact by M03 cannot be evaluated as the activity will start in M06. The eLearning catalogue aims to reach 1000+ trainees

Table 8 - Impact monitoring

8. Risks and Mitigations

The following table identifies risks identified during the first months of WP4 implementation and the corresponding risk-mitigation measures implemented so far. Risks with high severity have been mitigated a-priori. All risks - both those already-identified and potential new ones - are being continuously monitored at project runtime. New risks/mitigation measures arising from engagement activities will be managed as part of **Subtask 1.1.3 Risk management, ethics and IPR management**, under the responsibility of Trust-IT.

Risk Number	Risk Description	Proposed mitigation measure
R1	Lack of liaisons with pan-European & National initiatives Likelihood: Low Impact: High	Consortium members are exploiting established links with all major EC-recognised initiatives in Europe and globally: NEB, NEBC16, EIT, EIC, EOSC, ECTP (the European Construction and Technology Platform), CoR, Interreg, Covenant of the Mayors, EU Capitals of Culture, EU Green Capitals, EU Capitals of Innovation, EU Women Innovators, and more. Also, familiarity with and ease of access to the EC's DG CONNECT actors and projects (including close involvement with several "booster" initiatives: Horizon Results Booster, HSbooster.eu) is currently being leveraged to find relevant synergies for digiNEB's community (e.g. early adopters, the External Advisory Group, thematic working-group members). Participation in key events such as the Barcelona Smart Cities World Expo Congress and the OASC Connected Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities Conference has strengthened pan-European liaisons. Should difficulties arise in the project's next stages, activation of "Task Forces" will be sought, with win-win value propositions. Finally, concertation efforts will be initiated involving key stakeholders.
R2	Lack of engagement from relevant stakeholders Probability: Medium Impact: Medium	With their influential network and pan-European standing, all partners are committed to inherently mitigating the risk of lack of interest from target audiences. During the first months, digiNEB.eu has created meaningful relations to integrate with the NEB movement, creating a shared communication strategy. Moreover, it has also adopted and implemented a stakeholder management framework designed according to agile principles. Such an approach implies periodically assessing whether its approach is sufficiently inclusive and if the adequate target audience or candidates have shifted (also based on the feedback gathered from interacting with them. In the following months, digiNEB.eu will reinforce its efforts to attract the most challenging regional stakeholders, including the use of powerful networks and resources of partnering organisations such as strong alliances with the Committee of the Regions and Interreg Europe, all EU communication channels, and those that digiNEB.eu is synergising within the digital and industrial domains. Proactive use of communication channels by all partner networks will be engaged to inform about the breakthrough uses of technologies and stimulate widespread adoption.
R3	Capacity building and tech transfer difficulties	To mitigate risks of insufficient technological knowhow, capacity building effectiveness, and tech transfer bottlenecks, digiNEB.eu is engaging experienced facilitators (e.g. External Advisory Group ,

Risk Number	Risk Description	Proposed mitigation measure
	Probability: Low Impact: High	Early Adopters) and using well-established tested methodologies for rapid upskilling with novel technologies, such as those developed by partners TU Delft and ICF. ⁵ Through its open innovation platform, digiNEB.eu is fostering inclusive co-creation and exploitation of all NEB results in the wider business community (e.g. architects, designers, construction, creative sector, social actors), dedicated outputs for higher education and VET (see the success stories published so far in the observatory and the digital solutions included in the NEB Digital Toolkit).
R4	Lack of interoperability Probability: Low Impact: Low	Risks associated with the engagement of stakeholders include the establishment or replication of non-interoperable systems. This is not simply a technical problem of data, but a cultural and engagement problem often encountered when working with multidisciplinary communities with digital assets and data sets built within different systems to meet sector-specific standards. This may lead to the exclusion of large sections of potential stakeholders. As a mitigation strategy, the digiNEB.eu consortium ensures interoperability and ontology harmonisation across domains by sharing know-how from projects such as OntoCommons, a CSA dedicated to the standardisation of data documentation through harmonisation, standardisation and coordination, particularly in the realm of materials and manufacturing. Lessons and strategies from OntoCommons will inform digiNEB.eu approaches to stakeholder data.
R5	Being perceived as a fringe initiative Probability: Low Impact: Medium	Another risk identified by consortium partners is being seen as fringe or alternative and, therefore, not core to missions. As this is primarily an issue of communication and dissemination, digiNEB.eu is currently the key digital vehicle for engagement, learning, funding information and mapping overview across all programmes connected with NEB. An example is the promotion of the NEB academy, which will be carried out during the project's duration.
R6	Separation into silos Probability: Low Impact: Medium	The creation or reinforcement of existing silos within the wider digital and NEB communities provides a potential risk where different specialisms or groups within that community do not speak to each other, thereby preventing potential synergies and multidisciplinary possibilities and excluding those who may be made to feel they do not belong. Adopting thematic and mission-oriented approaches (e.g. thematic working groups, local workshops) provides an effective mitigation strategy, allowing for inclusion through interest rather than membership in a particular silo or specialism.
R7	Exclusion due to low digital skills Probability: Low Impact: High	Those with fewer digital skills or lower levels of digital access are at risk of exclusion. Providing introductory training in free, open-source tools that allow full participation will address this significant barrier for some valued community members. Examples include eLearning courses and other sector-specific training initiatives that

⁵ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00207543.2021.1989514>

Risk Number	Risk Description	Proposed mitigation measure
		will be organised according to specific needs. Additionally, using Thematic Working Groups instead of only Technical WGs can help reduce the risk of exclusion.
R8	Lack of evidence of co-creation Probability: Low Impact: Low	As it is vital for the digiNEB.eu project to align with NEB principles, the website and digital platform format allow effective contributions based on co-creation and not simply the delivery of results. Rather than act as a broadcast platform where the project announces its successes, the digiNEB.eu website constitutes a dynamic environment, with spaces dedicated to discussions and a user-friendly platform allowing individual contributions through a cost-free subscription. While live moderation can be resource-intensive, it acts as an effective form of online engagement when implemented in conjunction with the activity of Thematic and Technical Working Groups.
R9	Lack of incentive for participation Probability: Low Impact: High	In the co-creation of this engagement strategy plan, consortium partners identified a potential lack of incentive for participation. Risk mitigation strategies include using analytics and setting KPIs (either established in advance or developing live as a series of dynamic goals and indicators), developing new feedback mechanisms, and creating and disseminating tangible success stories (see digiNEB.eu observatory). The use of these measures allows for the demonstration of the effect of co-creation on engagement.

Table 9 – Risks and mitigations

Future risk scenarios that might arise during the execution will be notified to the Technical Project Coordinator (see Grant Agreement Section 2.3.4.1) in order to co-devise a mitigation plan to review the project objectives and detail a contingency plan to minimise the impact of the risk.

9. Conclusions

This deliverable describes the founding elements of digiNEB’s stakeholder engagement strategy, expanding on the planned actions to achieve the project's ambitious goals.

The main points described are:

- The digiNEB.eu community will be engaged not only by addressing each of the 7 distinct **Stakeholder Groups** (SGs) with the most appropriate value proposition for such a group but also through a mission-driven, thematic approach that bridges sectors, ensures interdisciplinarity and allows for self-selection by interest rather than simply targeting specific industries and professions.
- The engagement strategy will offer a diversity of **channels** to actively entice the various SGs, including online and physical events, social media and web platforms, the engagement of early adopters, the establishment of Thematic Working Groups, the publication of stakeholder success stories within the Digital Observatory, an eLearning Platform, an engaged and global External Advisory Group and the networks of existing NEB communities and projects.
- The detailing of a **plan of action** that orchestrates all engagement activities and outlines where support is expected from project partners.

- An overview of **monitoring activities** and tools will be carried out to measure and evaluate the project impact and feed that information into a dynamic engagement strategy that responds to these metrics.
- The relevant engagement **risks and mitigation actions** that require consideration in order to implement the engagement plan successfully.

A revised version of the “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report” is contractually expected in Month 18 (D4.2) and in Month 24 (D4.3). It is agreed among all Project Partners that the present document will be updated whenever changes are made to any of the topics described herein.

10. References

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Annex 1: Stakeholder groups and multiplier network

Stakeholder Group	Categories	Value proposition	Description	Multipliers
SG1	Architects, Designers, Engineers, and other professionals belonging to the NEB community	Support the identification of needs, gaps and requirements for the implementation of the NEB initiative, and contribute to NEB digitisation through the adoption of innovative, cutting-edge solutions, which will be displayed in the NEB digital toolkit and popularised by Thematic Working Groups and success stories.	Designers of buildings who adopt innovative digital solutions that contribute to bringing digitalisation to the New European Bauhaus. Creators of construction drawings who use NEB digital solutions to improve the quality of their pieces of work.	Official NEB partners, Architects' Council of Europe, Architectural Research European Network Association, Alliance for Solar Mobility, Culture Action Europe, Cumulus Association, Europa Nostra, Future Architecture platform, European Council of Engineers Chambers, European Council of Interior Architects, European Council of Spatial Planners, Local Governments for Sustainability, the European Region of the International Federation of Landscape Architects, Trans Europe Halles, German Academy for Urban and Regional Spatial Planning, Swiss Society of Engineers and Architects, FNCAUE, AACHEN BUILDING EXPERTS e.V. – ABE; ADC*E: Art Directors Club of Europe; AECEF – Association of European Civil Engineering Faculties; EU National Institutes for Culture (EUNIC); European Environmental Bureau; European Network of Cultural Centres, World Crafts Council Europe, New European Bauhaus' Friendship Group, NEB High Level Round Table, NEB Lab, International Federation of Landscape Architects, NEB Festival, Eurocities, European Network of Living Labs, European Fashion Heritage Association, Architects' Council of Europe (ACE), Architectural Research European Network Association (ARENA), Alliance for Solar Mobility (ASOM), Culture Action Europe (CAE), Cumulus Association, Europa Nostra, Future Architecture platform, European Council of Engineers Chambers (ECEC), European Council of Interior Architects (ECIA), European Council of Spatial Planners (ECTP), ELIA, ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability, IFLA Europe (European Region of the International Federation of Landscape Architects), Trans Europe Halles (TEH), German Academy for Urban and Regional Spatial Planning (DASL), Swiss Society of Engineers and Architects (SIA), FNCAUE, ENCORD European Network of Construction Companies for Research and Development.
SG2	Construction industry suppliers & other relevant industry	Support organisations with an appetite for gaining a role in the NEB arena and foster NEB-related	Construction engineers who benefit from adopting NEB digital solutions to optimise	European Construction, Built environment and Energy efficient Building Technology Platform (ECTP), World Green Buildings Council (WGBC), FIEC European Construction Industry Association (EU), Coalition for the Energy Efficiency of Buildings Europe (CEEB Europe), Forest-based Sector Technology Platform (FTP), Fire Safe Europe (FSEU), EOS European Organisation of the Sawmill Industry (EU), EPF European Panel Federation (EU), CEI-Bois European Woodworking Industry Confederation (EU), EFBWW European Federation of Building and

	<p>players, including start-ups, SMEs, associations in the building, mobility & health sectors, and SDOs</p>	<p>innovation facilitating cross-industry interactions among start-ups and SMEs in sectors such as mobility, planning and health.</p>	<p>building environments. Building organisations that foster NEB-related innovation facilitating cross-industry interaction.</p>	<p>Woodworkers (EU), EURADA European Association of Development Agencies* (EU), SSG Slovenski Gradbeni Grozd (Construction Cluster of Slovenia) (SI), UITP – The international association for public transport, MOVE EU, AVERE – the European Association for Electromobility, EIT Community Booster, European Digital SME Alliance, Enterprise Europe Network, StartUp Europe Partnership, Small Business Magazine, Essential Review – Europe Startup News, European Startup Association, Startup Europe Regions Network (SERN), Startup Europe Partnership (SEP), EU Startup Monitor, SMEUnited, SME Europe, European Small Business Alliance (ESBA), Small Business Standards (SBS), European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA), EBN (European Business and Innovation Centre Network), European Association of Craft and SMEs (UEAPME), EUROCHAMBRES, UNIFE- The Association of the European Rail Industry, AER- Association of European Radios, PGEU- Pharmaceutical Group of the European Union, ENTSO-E European Network of Transmission System Operators, EUROOPEN- European Organization for Packaging and the Environment, Built Environment Commons (FR), ACCIONIA (ES), ARUP (UK), Bouygues Construction (FR), EDF (FR), FCC (ES), STRABAG (DE), Uponor (FI), Focchi (IT), Mostostal (PL), CSBT (FR), Fraunhofer BIA (DE), RISE (SE), , TNO Built Environment (NL), VTT (FI), AITT (AT), BBRI (BE), Nobatek (FR), CNR-ISA (IT), FEUP (PT), TUM (DE), UPM Kymene Corporation* (FI), Business Joensuu (FI), Steinbeis entrumEuropa (DE), EURAC (IT), UNINOVA (PT), R2M Solution (IT), ETSI, Cen-Cenelec, oneM2M, HL7, IEEE, IEEE Cloud Computing, IEEE Future Networks, IEEE Smart Cities, iiRDS, ISO, IEC, ITU, IETF, OASIS, UN/CEFACT, W3C, CRSI – Concrete Reinforcing Steel Institute, Sheet Metal and Air Conditioning Contractors’ National Association (SMACNA), AES – Audio Engineering Society, CIE – International Commission on Illumination, IATA – International Air Transport Association, IUPAC – International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, NEMA – National Electrical Manufacturers Association, NIBSC – National Institute for Biological Standards and Control, IEA – International Energy Agency, NFPA – National Fire Protection Association, International Association of Oil & Gas Producers (IOGP), IATA – International Air Transport Association, IUPAC – International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, NEMA – National Electrical Manufacturers Association, Bauhaus Construction LTD, European Confederation of Woodworking Industries (CEI-Bois), European Panel Federation (EPF), European Federation of Building and Woodworkers (EFBWW), European Factory Platform, European Factories of the Future, FoodDrinkEurope, European Federation of Associations of Health Product Manufacturers (EHPM), Shift2Rail, FNTF Fédération Nationale des Travaux Publics (FR), IVL (SE), BAM (DE), IERC (IE), StoraEnso (SE), SLC – Standards Leadership Council, United Nations Forum on Sustainability Standards (UNFSS),</p>
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				FairTrade International, ISO/TC 130 Graphic technology, ISO/TC 59/SC 13 Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM), ISO/TC 38 Textiles, ISO/TC 89 Wood-based panels, ISO/TC 215 Health informatics, ISO/TC 268 Sustainable cities and communities, ISO/TC 287 Sustainable processes for wood and wood-based products, AFNOR, ASRO, Austrian Standards, BSI, DIN, DPS, ILNAS, IPQ, ISBIH, IST, LST, LVS, NBN, NEN, NSAI, PKN, SFS, SIS, SIST, Standard Norge, UNE, UNI.
SG3	Research and academia	Proactively find stimuli for new research and publications by favouring the sharing of knowledge and learning, educating the next generation of leaders in the NEB digital domains.	Scientists that educate the next generation of leaders in NEB and digital domains by sharing knowledge.	European PPPs and Project Consortia – European Partnership for Key Digital Technologies, Processes4Planet – Transforming the European Process Industry for a sustainable society, People-centric sustainable built environment (Built4People), specific Horizon projects related to building/construction/urban transformation (e.g. BuildInWood, Basajaun). Past, ongoing and upcoming H2020 & HE Research projects & related outcomes, including the NEB lighthouse demonstrators, DIGITbrain, Rubizmo, CityZen, RURITAGE, UNISECO, BLUEfasma, OASIS, NextGen Micro cities, Integr@tención, mySMARTLife, e-MOPOLI, BIG HIT, EPIU GETAFE, INCIRCLE’S MISSION, CIVITAS DESTINATIONS, AURORAL, dRural, SmartX – The European Smart Textiles Accelerator, RE-DWELL, MobiliseSME, Wood4Bauhaus, DigiPlace, – European Partnership for Key Digital Technologies (KDT), Processes4Planet – Transforming the European Process Industry for a sustainable society, People-centric sustainable built environment (Built4People), NEB lighthouse demonstrators, European Digital Innovation Hubs – EDIH such as AIR4S – Artificial Intelligence & Robotics for Sustainable Development Goals, Application Center for Automation in Healthcare, ASSIST4SME – Digital Transformation of SME through Assistive Systems in Production, ASTURIAS DIGITAL INNOVATION HUB, Belgian Building Research Institute (BBRI), Brussels Creative, CETMA – Technologies Design and Materials European Research Centre, Cluster ICT, media and creative industries Berlin-Brandenburg, Cluster of Sustainable Building of Andalusia, Connected Mobility Hub, CONNECT5, Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (DASAI), DIGIS3 – Smart, Sustainable and Cohesive Digitalization, DigIT Hub Sweden, Digital Health-Biosciences (DIH-bio), Digital Innovation Hub for Society (DIH4S), Digital Innovation Hub for 3D printing (3DJPU), DIH for digital twins of logistics systems and manufacturing processes and systems (DIH_DiTMaPS), Good Life for Finland, GreenSupplyChain DIH, HPC-Cloud and Cognitive Systems for Smart Manufacturing processes, Robotics and Logistics, Living Lab for Smart Society (LL4SS), Plastipolis, Smart Connected Supplier Network, SmartCityTech, Research Association (EFFRA), European Factory Platform, European Factories

				of the Future Enterprise Europe Network, Architectural Research Network (ARENA), European Regions Research and Innovation Network (ERRIN), DIHNET.EU project.
SG 4	Digital technology companies & associations	Support the uptake of digital solutions and services relevant to the NEB initiative while creating a competitive advantage by testing and implementing new digital solutions and services.	Tech ecosystem that supports the uptake of digital solutions relevant to the NEB initiative through testing and implementing new digital services.	Blockchain Observatory Forum, IT Security Portal, TechNative, TechNativeLive, CloudPro, Tech Radar, IEEE IoT Journal, Artificial Intelligence Top News, ITProPortal, Net Technologies, Digital Twin Hub, Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation, Big Data Value AssociationEuropean Federation of Food Science and Technology (EFFoST), The European Technologies Industries (Orgalim aisbl), AI4EU, CISPE Cloud, CyberSec EU, Digital EU, ECSO, EIT Climate, EIT Digital, EIT InnoEnergy, Horizon Cloud Forum, INATBA, EIT, OFE – Open Forum Europe, Quantum Flagship, TNO, AIOTI, CEINMAT (ES), TECNALIA Foundation (ES), DTI (DK), SINTEF (NO), EMPA (CH), 5G ACIA, ATIS (Alliance for Telecommunications Industry Solutions), DIGITAL EUROPE, TechNative, TechNativeLive, CloudPro, The Register, ITProPortal, SourceSecurity.com, IT Security Portal, Tech Radar, Net Technologies, European AI Alliance, IEEE IoT Journal, IEEE Communications Society, Research Europe, TCT Magazine, Artificial Intelligence Top News, Telensa, Inputech, Tech Nation, ACD Group, AEG ID, Asygn, AXEM Technology, Lab ID, Thales DIS BPS, ARGO Vision, Unify, SmartBot Parking, SMEunited, EIT Digital, Digital SME Alliance.
SG 5	Policy Makers, including Green Deal-related	Contribute to bridging EU policies and industry activities, supporting the design of policies at the intersection between NEB actors and digital players, and facilitating the future deployment of NEB initiatives.	European authorities that support the design and implementation of European policies at the intersection between NEB actors and digital players.	Open Innovation Strategy and Policy Group (OISPG), The European Environmental Bureau, European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, European Environment Information and Observation Network, European Environment Agency, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), CEA (FR), GHG Protocol, ECOS, Carbon Trust, Green IT. Also, the European Commission - DG CONNECT, DG GROW, DG DIGIT, DG JRC, DG CLIMA, DG ECFIN, DG ENER, DG ENV, DG MOVE, DG REGIO, DG RTD, EU Environment.
SG 6	National & regional authorities, mayors (including	Upskill in the digital domain to improve cities' liveability, boost efficiency and effectiveness in	Regional and National authorities that support the design and	NEB Lighthouses, all EU Capitals of Culture, all EU Green Capitals, all EU Capitals of Innovation, Members of the Covenant of the Mayors, ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability, Council of European Municipalities and Regions (CEMR), Local Governments and Municipal Authorities Constituency (LGMA), European Federation Local Authority Chief Executive Officers, United Cities and Local Governments (UCLG), Global Taskforce of Local and Regional Governments, the

	urban planners) and cities	project management, and facilitate the transformation of research results into concrete initiatives at the local level.	implementation of local policies at the intersection between NEB actors and digital players.	Urban Development Network, the Smart Cities Marketplace, the EU Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy, EUROCITIES, the Union for the Mediterranean, the City Science initiative, Cities Mission, Climate Adaptation Mission, the Urban Development Network, the Smart Cities Marketplace, the EU Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy, EUROCITIES, the Union for the Mediterranean, the City Science initiative; this SG includes also representatives from the Committee of the Regions, Interreg Europe, Regional Governments from across the EU Member States.
SG 7	Civil society organisations and citizens	Increase awareness of NEB, promoting the adoption of its values related to the importance of sustainability, inclusiveness and aesthetics in living spaces to achieve a better quality of life.	Promoters of the NEB values and its adoption in living spaces to achieve a better quality of life.	Cradle to Cradle NGO, S-COM SUSTAINABLE COMMUNICATION AISBL, Air Pollution & Climate Secretariat (AIRCLIM), Global Atmospheric Pollution Forum, European Federation for Transport and Environment T&E, Danish Ecological Council (DOR), Rethink Plastic, EUROOPEN- European Organization for Packaging and the Environment, People-Centered Smart Cities, Civil Society Europe, European Foundation Centre, Civic Space Watch, Green10, Placemaking Western Balkans, DoCoMoMo International, Citizen Science Lab at Leiden University, EU-citizen.science platform, ECSA – European Citizen Science Association, The Great Transformation.